

Deliverable D2.1.1

Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures

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Overview

This paper serves two purposes: firstly, to document the service integration procedures developed in Base and, secondly, to explain the concepts underlying the actual tasks to be done in the Integration Phase.

“Service integration” addresses different but interdependent developments of both the service teams and Task Area 2 of Base4NFDI:

- The service teams take the service from the prototypical state it reached in the initialisation phase to a fully developed and functional one. The steps for this are described in the work programme of the integration proposal, and the concrete objectives are defined by corresponding *service-specific deliverables and milestones*.
- Base4NFDI is developing the framework, the service lifecycle management, and procedures of the future service portfolio of the NFDI, as described in the Base4NFDI proposal¹ and summarised by corresponding *Base deliverables*.

Base4NFDI supports the service teams in building their services in such a way that they not only fit into the service landscape of the NFDI in a coherent and quality-assured manner, but are also interoperable in a wider context, e. g., the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This becomes most evident in the three Base deliverables which are not only due at the end of the Integration Phase and mark its successful completion, but as well link the two development strands of the service team and Base:

- D2.4.1 - Report on conducted service integration,
- D2.4.3 - Report on results of quality and sustainability studies,
- D2.4.4 - Report on portfolio admission for a given service.

It's TA2's responsibility to concretise these Base deliverables, which was done subject to two essential requirements: Firstly, the fulfilment of the own service-specific goals and deliverables by the teams must be utilised as contributions to the fulfilment of the Base deliverables and, secondly, the teams should be burdened as little as possible with additional tasks besides their own work packages.

Notice

This document refers to the status of Base4NFDI's developments in September 2025. Many aspects are still under discussion, particularly with regard to the scope and functionalities of the upcoming service portfolio, which will affect workflows and responsibilities. Any adjustments to these will be addressed in revised versions of this report.

¹ “Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI”, <https://zenodo.org/records/10245518>

What to do and when

The following scheme represents what is to be done by Base4NFDI (beige) and service teams (green) during the integration process. The service team's own workplan, tasks, and deliverables mark the starting and pivotal point of these activities, and the Base deliverables D2.4.x the final goal.

Most importantly, the service team is asked to follow its work plan and deliver the outputs as shown. Secondly, the team is asked to document its success in developing the service, the quality, maturity, interoperability and sustainability of the service, and to provide a set of metadata required for inclusion of the service in the future service portfolio. Bases4NFDI is responsible for supporting the teams with appropriate templates and guidelines and mapping the teams' individual deliverables to the overarching deliverables of Base itself. Finally, Base4NFDI will formally sign off on the fulfilment of the latter, confirming the successful completion of the Integration Phase. At this point, the service team should announce the completion of the Integration Phase, at least by a contribution to the Base4NFDI newsletter and website.

The three base deliverables are high-level and in part depending on each other, and are therefore not suitable for organising the actual work of the service teams. To this end, TA2 and Service Stewards have compiled a service-oriented set of separate and mutually independent deliverables ("D.Int.X") which can be processed individually. Together with a detailed schedule and instructions and templates for documenting the results, these are

explained in a separate document intended as a practical guide for integration and the tasks related to it.²

A clear distinction between the respective responsibilities is especially important because the shape of the future portfolio and possible adjustments of the Base deliverables will depend on the suggestions of the NFDI Task Force on Governance and Sustainability,³ a discussion the service teams are not involved in.

Integration (D2.4.1)

During the Integration Phase, the service shall mature into an "integrated" one which for reasons of practicability is defined as

the **integrated service**

1. has been **adopted for use by NFDI**
2. and is **interoperable with other services.**

Tasks of the service team

The team will have to provide reports on both the adoption and interoperability of their service as well as at least two success stories based on practical experience. It is up to the teams whether they create two separate reports on adoption and interoperability, a single report on both topics, or if they include these topics in the success stories. In any case, the report(s) should be concise, comprehensible, and plausible, and there are no specific requirements with respect to formatting, length, and so on. Further details and a template of how the stories could be structured can be found in the appendix.

Adoption

Adoption should be documented by a plausible demonstration that the service is used in the consortia because of its added value, the closure of gaps, enhanced possibilities, ease of use, replacement of legacy services, etc. Relating directly to the objectives of the service development and the extent to which they have been achieved, this can be shown regardless of whether the service is purely technical or essentially non-technical.

Interoperability

Interoperability can be demonstrated by various characteristics that show that the service utilises relevant open standards. These can refer to different contexts, not all of which might be applicable to a particular service: technical, semantic, operational, or legal. Again, as with adoption, this is closely related to the goals of service development and the service team should come up with a plausible demonstration of their achievements and

² "Requirements for Completion of the Integration Phase", <https://zenodo.org/records/17107045>

³ "Arbeitsplan 2025 der TFGS", <https://zenodo.org/records/15181340>

show that the service consolidates standards or workflows, links different interfaces and protocols, harmonises existing services, fits into other entities, employs other basic services, etc.

Success stories

The service teams shall provide at least two success stories: One from contextually related consortia and one from a non-related one, to show that the service has been built fit for purpose and that it is suitable for other contexts as well, respectively. Outcomes of incubator projects would naturally be a good basis here.

Tasks of Base4NFDI

TA2 will support the teams by providing more guidance on these reports. The service stewards will help to identify potential incubators and set them on the right path.

At the end of the Initialisation Phase, TA2 will (if necessary with the help of the service stewards) review the reports and the tracked results and confirm that all requirements in terms of content have been met, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. The “conducted service integration” will formally be documented in OpenProject.

Due date

The reports should be available **towards the end of the Integration Phase**.

Quality and sustainability (D2.4.3)

The Base4NFDI proposal lists two measures to ensure an adequate quality and sustainability of a service: Firstly, the service should move from a technology readiness level (TRL) of 5-6 after initialisation to TRL 7-8 after integration. Secondly, appropriate studies must be carried out that not only look at the service or software quality itself, but also at its usability and the extent to which it meets the needs of users. These achievements will have to be documented accordingly.

Tasks of the service team

Service maturity

With respect to the decision process of Base4NFDI, service maturity is expressed in terms of technological readiness.⁴ Even if a service is only partially - if at all - a technical one, the TRL concept should be used to document that the service has been developed accordingly. In a general sense, TRL 5-6 (achieved after initialisation) can be attributed to

⁴ <https://base4nfdi.de/process/criteria-for-basic-services>

a prototype that provides essential components and has been tested by a limited number of users in a limited environment. TRL 7-8 (after integration) would then apply to a fully implemented service that is regularly utilised in the actually intended environment. (Further development towards a fully-fledged scale-out and long-term implementation is left for the subsequent Ramp-Up Phase.)

These definitions can be applied to any type of service and their fulfilment may be checked according to the concrete service-specific tasks and deliverables. Examples of this are given in the appendix. The team must provide a summary report demonstrating plausibly that the service has achieved an appropriate level at the end of the Integration Phase.

Software quality

To ensure high software quality, the service teams are asked to go through a procedure of self-assessment three times, two of which are during the Integration Phase: at the time of application for the Ramp-Up Phase after about 18 months and at the end of the Integration Phase. To this end, TA2 provides a check list of relevant quality criteria the service teams are asked to fill in (see appendix).

Usability

The team should identify service-relevant use cases or workflows and test the prototype of the service using these scenarios in close cooperation with potential users. The work programme should be adapted to address unmet or changed needs, to abandon components that are not needed, and to modify concepts that are not applicable. Tests, lessons learned, and modifications of the work packages should be documented in a comprehensive and concise manner.

For compliance with the UI/UX standards (see appendix), the service teams are meeting with TA2 at least once per project phase, to discuss their status and possible measures to improve. If applicable, the compliance will be reviewed systematically by the TA2 team as part of usability evaluation TA2 will conduct. Service teams are encouraged to provide areas of interest where usability evaluations would be beneficial. Service teams are expected to assist the evaluation by providing access to potential users, stakeholders, and prototypes as needed and available.

Operation concept

An important component of sustainability will be an operation concept which should be drafted in cooperation with the intended operators of the service and indicate the personnel and infrastructure resources required for running the service. During the Ramp-Up Phase, this shall be further developed into a business model which addresses costs, financing, organisational form (like association, limited liability company). The operation concept is part of the requirements for admittance of the service to the service portfolio (cf. below).

Tasks of Base4NFDI

TA2 will aid the team in adapting the TRL concept to their specific context and to identify from their work programme the relevant, applicable concepts.

In order to clarify any misinterpretations or misunderstandings regarding the software quality criteria as quickly as possible, TA2 is happy to organise meetings with the team. TA2 will assist with the completion of the checklist and help interpreting the detailed quality criteria with respect to the aims of service. The team is encouraged to request support at any time.

TA2 will also help to identify suitable use cases and to conduct formal usability evaluations in order to systematically review the UI/UX compliance of the service. Based on the results, we will produce a report, as well as recommendations for usability improvements. TA2 will also provide consultations on usability evaluations conducted as part of the service's project plan.

To facilitate the development of an operation concept / business model, TA2 will provide a set of templates and guides that are targeted to different, typically to be expected technical and non-technical service contexts.

As explained above for D2.4.1, TA2 and TA3 will confirm the fulfilment of all sustainability and quality requirements. Successful completion is formally documented in OpenProject.

Due dates

The **user studies** should be carried out at an **early stage of the Integration Phase**.

The first **software quality assessment** should be completed **before applying for the Ramp-Up Phase**.

The **final reports and the second software assessment** should be available **towards the end of the Integration Phase**.

Portfolio admittance (D2.4.4)

Regardless of what form the future NFDI portfolio will take, a common set of metadata is needed for each service. Additionally, the services must meet some standards to be included. Otherwise, the portfolio could not be operated effectively and consistently. This results in a set of *portfolio-related requirements* (cf. appendix) to be fulfilled during the Integration Phase. Most of these are descriptive and, according to experience with the services currently being developed, almost all are already addressed by the respective

initialisation and integration proposals and, more precisely, the service-specific deliverables therein.

Tasks of the service team

First of all, the teams should take note of these requirements, but also be aware that much of the needed information is already in their hands since the beginning of the Initialisation Phase, and additional information will emerge as the service is being developed. It is primarily a matter of recording the information as soon as it becomes available.

However, there are some more complex descriptions that will have to be provided by the service teams, especially with regard to

- the capabilities and limitations of the service, (if applicable, service level agreements),
- an operation concept,
- a suitable set of key performance indicators.

For these, the teams can resort to guides and templates that will be provided by Base4NFDI. Again, the resulting descriptions should be concise, comprehensible, and plausible with respect to the context of the service.

Tasks of Base4NFDI

TA2 and the service stewards will compile the necessary templates on capabilities/limitations, operation concepts, KPIs, and, if required, other topics. During the development of the service, they will help to map and abstract the results achieved there to the portfolio-relevant deliverables. They will provide a suitable electronic system for recording all required information and tracking the fulfilment of the deliverables, and monitor the progress in this regard.

Again, TA2 and TA3 will confirm the fulfilment of all portfolio-related requirements. Successful completion is formally documented in OpenProject.

Due dates

The metadata and descriptions should be given **towards the end of the Integration Phase**, except:

Service provider, owner/manager, and support contact need to be given **after 18 months**, as this is relevant for the application for the Ramp-Up Phase,

Appendix / further documents

Adoption (for D2.4.1)

Adoption means essentially that a service is employed and utilised by individuals, communities, or consortia because it

- provides an added value to the users,
- closes thematic, methodological, or functional gaps which previously prevented effective work,
- creates new opportunities,
- expands or enhances existing possibilities,
- simplifies, streamlines, or harmonises existing methods, workflows, or access to resources that have been in place before

for

- better scientific research,
- more efficient data analysis and management,
- easier archival and dissemination of results,
- improved sharing of data, methods, concepts, and so on.

Every Base4NFDI service is being built around objectives like these and the most obvious starting point for documenting adoption would be the respective goals the service team has laid out in their initialisation and integration work plans. If applicable already in the Integration Phase, initial KPI numbers or diagrams might serve as further confirmation to this end.

Interoperability (for D2.4.1)

To be interoperable, a service will have to adhere to and utilise context-relevant open standards. Depending on the given context and purpose, this can relate to different aspects:

- technical: application interfaces, transfer protocols,
- semantic: metadata standards, terminologies, identifier systems,
- operational: methods, workflows, best practices,
- legal: GDPR, data protection, accessibility, access regulations, service/data security.

In addition, and due to the nature of Base4NFDI itself, each service should consider different scopes of interoperability:

- internal: a service is built to harmonise already existing services of the consortia,
- external: a service targets other entities like previously unrelated consortia, NFDI, EOSC.

Not every aspect might be relevant for a particular service. But again, the objectives for setting up the service have been defined in the proposals and work plans for initialisation and integration, and the interoperability of the service can be documented according to these goals.

Success stories (for D2.4.1)

Success stories should illustrate in a comprehensive and concise manner what the service (team) has practically achieved in terms of adoption and interoperability. They can help to briefly communicate selected results of the Integration Phase and describe the integration and anchoring of basic services with NFDI stakeholders. These stories should be based on actual, practical experience and refer to

- specific use cases as described in the integration proposal,
- concrete improvements based on user studies,
- outcomes of incubator projects or use cases.

There should be at least two success stories, one related to the use cases of consortia, institutions, or working groups involved in the construction of the service, and one related to use cases of other entities that have not been involved so far. When appropriate and at the discretion of the service team, the success stories can include more general documentation on adoption and interoperability, making these two separate reports superfluous.

Template for success stories

Success stories should focus on

- added value and benefits for research,
- service adoption and usage in consortia and communities,
- integration with existing NFDI services and resources,
- interoperability with standards used in the NFDI and internationally,
- collaborations with other Basic Services,
- incubator projects.

The following table suggests a structure for such stories. Feel free to customize it to your needs and/or the context of your service.

Topic	Focus/scope
Basic Service	Name of the integrated service (component)
Collaboration partners such as consortia, communities, services	Names of the NFDI consortia involved and specific TAs, communities, services

Challenges	Short description of the challenges or requirements the involved consortia faced and which the service is intended to address
Approach	Short description of the approach and solution
Results	Concrete benefits and improvements for the involved consortia, according to the results of the project; links and references to deployments and documentation
Timeframe	Duration of the project
Involved (optional)	List of key persons or teams
Lessons learned (optional)	Important learnings from the process, either for the context of Bas4NFDI, the consortia, or other projects
Next steps (optional)	Planned further developments or adaptations

TRLs (for D2.4.3)

As outlined above, service teams should demonstrate that their service is sufficiently mature towards the end of the Integration Phase. The technology readiness levels⁵ employed by the Base4NFDI process may not be easy to grasp for non-technical services. Here we exemplify how this concept could be applied in such cases,

- starting with **TRL 5-6 after initialisation**
= the service is validated/demonstrated in a relevant environment
- and reaching **TRL 7-8 after integration**
= the service is fully qualified and operational

For a **consulting framework or helpdesk**:

- **TRL 5-6:** The framework is tested with a small group of representative clients and demonstrated across multiple scenarios.
- **TRL 7-8:** The framework is fully implemented with early adopters and proven through successful outcomes.

For a system of **standards, best practices, or workflows**:

- **TRL 5-6:** The practices/standards are refined based on feedback and have been shown to be effective.
- **TRL 7-8:** The practices/standards are documented, consistently applied across various projects, and harmonised in a comprehensive system.

⁵ <https://base4nfdi.de/process/criteria-for-basic-services>

For an **information hub, e. g., on metadata and terminologies:**

- **TRL 5-6:** The hub is deployed with core functionalities and feedback mechanisms and tested with diverse datasets and user communities.
- **TRL 7-8:** Advanced features (like interoperability with other systems) are added, the hub achieves scalability and reliability and meets community needs effectively.

For a **training catalogue or a a train-the-trainer curriculum:**

- **TRL 5-6:** Trainings are tested with a pilot group, curriculum is reviewed by subject matter experts and pilot trainers, materials are revised and improved based on feedback and are delivered to a small group of users or trainers.
- **TRL 7-8:** Trainings/curriculum are rolled out to a wider audience and integrated into regular offerings, advanced features are added, support structures are in place.

Statements of this kind can be directly related to the tasks and deliverables of the work programmes that the service teams have set up for the Integration Phase.

Software quality (for D2.4.3)

Base4NFDI defined 8 categories of software quality criteria:

- *Accessibility & Availability.* **Accessibility** is the degree to which a product or system can be used by people with the widest range of diversity and capabilities to achieve a specified goal in a concrete context of use. **Availability** is the degree to which a system, product, or component is operational and accessible when required for use.
- *Attractiveness.* **Attractiveness** is the degree to which a user interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction, including topics like internationalisation and localisation.
- *Confidentiality & Safety.* **Confidentiality** is the degree to which a product or system ensures that data are accessible only to those who have been authorised access. **Safety** is the degree to which a product or system mitigates the potential personal risk to humans or to system components, in the intended contexts of use.
- *Documentation.*
- *Fault tolerance.* **Fault tolerance** is the degree to which a system, product, or component operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.
- *Modifiability & Maintainability.* **Modifiability** is the degree to which a product or system can be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading the product. **Maintainability** is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified by the intended maintainers.
- *Performance.* **Performance** is how well the system works taking into account the amount of resources used under stated conditions.
- *Testability.* **Testability** is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which test criteria can be established for a system, product, or component [1]. It is connected strongly to modifiability.

Within these categories, different criteria are relevant depending on the user context - cf. list below. In Base4NFDI, we consider 3 user groups:

1. Developers
2. System administrators
3. End users - scientists

Supported by TA2, the teams themselves should assess which of the criteria listed below apply to their service and whether the service or software fulfils the criteria. This self-assessment should take place three times:

1. Application for the Ramp-Up Phase
2. End of Integration Phase
3. End of Ramp-Up Phase

A detailed list of criteria and a description of when to address these during the self-assessments is given in an accompanying document.⁶

UI/UX standards (for D2.4.3)

The service should comply with usability standards from the following categories:

- **General principles:** consistency, accessibility, responsiveness, efficiency, feedback & validation
- **Visual Design:** typography, color scheme, spacing & layout, icons & images
- **Navigation:** hierarchy, breadcrumbs, search functionality, minimized cognitive load
- **Interaction and feedback:** buttons & clickables, hover & focus states, loading indicators, error handling

More detailed information is provided in an accompanying document.⁷

Portfolio-related requirements (for D2.4.4)

As said, a service must meet a number of requirements in order to be part of the NFDI service portfolio. These were chosen based on following premises:

- There must be as few requirements as possible.
- The service teams must be able to fulfil them during each of the two years of the Integration Phase.
- The criteria must already ensure a basic compatibility with EOSC requirements.

⁶ "Notes on software quality", <https://zenodo.org/records/15235863>

⁷ "Notes on usability", <https://zenodo.org/records/15235863>

Most of the criteria are about descriptions from the following categories:

- **General:** one-page service description; list of service categories/tags (cf. below); link to any further description; URL of the hosted service; imprint of the hosting institution; consent of the institution to have the service published; list of involved NFDI consortia; list other related services
- *from the Initialisation Phase: service name; 1-line short description*
- **Contact:** names and mail addresses of the service manager and a 1st-level support; description of communication channels between the service provider and the Base4NFDI portfolio management
- *from the initialisation phase: name and mail address of the service owner*
- **Conditions:** description of service quality and limitations (cf. below)
- **Users:** description of registration and authorisation steps at the user's side
- *from the initialisation phase: confirmation that the service employs IAM4NFDI*
- **Security:** name and/or mail address of the security incident contact; information on the service's geographical location
- **Legal:** description of fees/charges
- *from the initialisation phase: confirmation that the service is provided not for profit and free of ads*
- **Operation concept/KPIs:** draft of operation concept; list of tangible performance indicators (cf. below)
- **Base4NFDI:** D2.4.1, D2.4.3 as explained above
- *from the initialisation phase: D1.4.1 to D1.4.5⁸*

Further details are given in an accompanying document,⁹ and more information on service categories, limitations/capabilities, and KPIs can be found below. There will be no specific template to fill in, but TA2 will provide an electronic form for entering and keeping all relevant information.

Service categories

In order to be able to search for suitable services in the portfolio, the services must be categorised, and the service teams should choose from the following list between two and five categories which apply best to their service:

- Cloud Infrastructure
- Communication
- Computing
- Data Analysis
- Data Management
- Electronic Lab Notebook
- Identifiers
- Knowledge Base
- Knowledge Graph
- Planning
- Publication
- Software
- Survey
- Terminology
- Training
- Virtual Research Environment
- Other

⁸ "Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase", <https://zenodo.org/records/15020379>

⁹ "Notes on portfolio requirements", <https://zenodo.org/records/15235863>

Service capabilities and limitations

There don't need to be full-blown service level agreements (SLAs). However, potential users of the service need to know what they can expect. To this end, the service teams should provide a short description of what users may rely on. Depending on the service, this could include indications of

- what the service users can expect, like:
 - service availability, like regular downtimes or “99 %”,
 - helpdesk, support and response times,
 - provided storage or CPU resources, like “GB per user” or “CPU hours per job”,
 - allowed number of requests, like “PID generations per day” or “trouble tickets per month”,
 - persistence of uploaded data between sessions or times for which data are kept,
 - training, consultation, and knowledge,
- and what not, for example:
 - development of specific software,
 - manual processing of data.

Ultimately, a “best effort” statement or something similar would be fine as well.

Performance indicators

After the integration and Ramp-Up Phase, the life cycle of the service moves on to the operational phase and, eventually, to the decommissioning of the service. Adequate monitoring is required to track the adoption and success of the service and a set of performance metrics that are relevant, objective and measurable for the service is needed. Although they are mainly relevant for the operational phase, KPIs can already be helpful during the integration and start-up phases to document the progress made in these phases.

Possible metrics could refer to the following categories, and an extensive list of options can be found in our *Notes on KPIs*.¹⁰

- **Users:**
 - **Persons/groups:** number of users or of working groups, total / per day, ...
 - **Scope:** number of involved consortia, number of workshops, publications, subscribers, page visits, ...
- **Usage:**
 - **Resources:** CPU time, storage, data volume transferred, ...
 - **Items:** number of commits, posts, tickets, files, folders, PIDs, ...
 - **Instances:** number of virtual machines, Jupyter applications, projects, ...

¹⁰ “Notes on KPIs”, <https://zenodo.org/records/15235863>

The Basic Services currently developed are too diverse to define a “core” or mandatory set of KPIs. Instead, the service teams are asked to select approximately two user-related and two usage-related indicators each that are applicable to the service. If possible, they should provide different figures to differentiate between, e. g., users from NFDI consortia and others. Guidance on this can also be found in the *Notes on KPIs*. Base4NFDI will provide a scheme and a technical platform for collecting and aggregating the raw figures on a regular schedule.

Acknowledgement

Many of these concepts have been inspired by what HIFIS¹¹ (Helmholtz Federated IT Services) has built up in recent years to bring services together in a standardised catalogue and manage them jointly. We would like to thank the HIFIS team for many fruitful and committed discussions.

¹¹ <https://hifs.net>